

Effects of SR insurance company marketing strategy on their sales

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Abstract

In recent years, with the opening of the market and the relaxation of national policies, China's bancassurance market has developed rapidly. SR Company is one of the earliest foreign insurance companies established in China. With the rise of domestic bancassurance businesses, the growth of corporate premiums has been showing a rapid development trend. However, with the increase in market players, the impact of foreign financial institutions, and the impact of the financial crisis, SR's bancassurance business is facing the dilemma of reduced premium income and a shrinking market share. Improving the core competitiveness of the company's products has become a strategic choice for the company to deal with the changes in the banking market. This paper, based on the work experience and thinking of planning, supervision, training, and other posts in the bancassurance business of SR Company, combined with the theoretical knowledge and the detailed investigation, deeply analyzed the problems existing in the bancassurance business of SR Company and the causes of the problems, and on the basis of studying and referring to the successful experiences of peers at home and abroad, put forward the development ideas of innovative marketing as well as better carrying out the bancassurance business marketing strategy and business philosophy. First of all, the article expounds the basic theory and function of bancassurance business, the concept, characteristics, and strategies of insurance marketing, and on this basis analyzes the external opportunities and threats, internal strengths and weaknesses faced by the company, and analyzes the strengths and opportunities strategy, weaknesses and opportunities strategy, strengths and threats strategy, and weaknesses and threats strategy, and puts forward corresponding countermeasures. Secondly, it analyzes the basic status quo of the bancassurance business of SR Company in terms of business scale, marketing channels, main products, customer relations, and sales teams, and deeply analyzes the problems in the product structure, bancassurance cooperation, marketing channels, and product promotion of the bancassurance business marketing of the company. Finally, in view of the outstanding problems in the marketing of bancassurance products, the company proposed marketing countermeasures and improvement measures for bancassurance business in four aspects: product innovation, marketing channel innovation, marketing team building, and brand promotion strategy.

Keywords: Bancassurance; Marketing strategy; SWOT analysis.

To cite this article:

Fan, Z., & Matamis, J. G. (2021). Effects of SR insurance company marketing strategy on their sales. *The Executives*, 2, 95-106.

Introduction

With the gradual deepening of the trend of economic integration, international financial liberalization, and globalization in various countries, the banking operating environment and system have changed significantly under the stimulation of information technology, innovation in financial means, and

the intersection of international capital markets. The structural model, operating mode, system, and competition pattern of the world financial industry are changing. Under the conditions of this change and constant change, the traditional business of banks providing financial services such as financing and settlement for the international trade, production, and manufacturing service industries has been affected. The cost and income are decreasing day by day. Facing the pressure of survival and the need to urgently develop new businesses, banks continue to look for new profit growth points, capital sources, and flow methods. At the same time, due to the transformation, the business boundaries of banking, financial securities, and insurance are becoming increasingly blurred, and bancassurance comes into being.

The bancassurance business originated in France in the 1970s, which caused a global financial shock as soon as it appeared (Ricci, 2012). After 80 years, with economic globalization and the growth of financial business, the bancassurance business has achieved rapid expansion. Although the development of bancassurance is only about 30 years old, in Europe and other countries, especially France, bancassurance accounts for most of the premium income, which is closely related to the policies of the financial industry (Richez-Battesti & Leseul, 2016). The extensive development of bancassurance has achieved remarkable results. At the same time, the traditional insurance institutions that only underwrite risks are also gradually developing into modern insurance enterprises that operate underwriting and investment, and the penetration of insurance enterprises into the financial market and monetary capital market is becoming stronger and stronger. Under this complex and changeable background, bancassurance is characterized by the mutual penetration of insurance business and banking business and the relationship between insurance capital and bank capital. It is the product of mutual integration, insurance products, and banking products. It is a complex process integrating business channel innovation, business product innovation, management system innovation, and work mechanism organization mode innovation.

Since the great development of bancassurance business in the 1980s, the amount of bancassurance business in France, Italy, Britain, and Switzerland has accounted for more than 70% of the total life insurance premium; Singapore in Southeast Asia and Hong Kong in China have also made significant achievements in the development of bancassurance business; North America, Japan, South Korea, and other developed countries, although starting slowly, have also made significant progress and shown a trend of rapid expansion. In China, the bancassurance business has grown from scratch and gradually developed (Floreddu, 2013). Since 1995, major domestic banks and large insurance companies have started to try to cooperate with each other. Insurance companies have signed agency agreements with banks, and bancassurance has gradually emerged. After the slow development of bancassurance business in the first few years, in the 21st century, with the impact of the rapid leap forward of the domestic economy, bancassurance business has also entered the “blowout” development stage. There has been fierce competition among domestic insurance companies, and banks have become the focus of their mutual competition. Because the bancassurance business is one of the main sources of their income. At present, almost all domestic insurance institutions, especially newly established insurance companies, focus on the development of bancassurance businesses. With the deepening of cooperation between insurance institutions and banking enterprises, a comprehensive cooperation agreement has been signed to vigorously develop the bancassurance consignment business, gradually forming a new pattern of business penetration, complementary advantages, mutual benefit, and common development between insurance and banks in China.

SR Insurance Company is formed by a Beijing commercial bank with the most growth potential in China and a diversified financial group in the Netherlands with a world-renowned reputation, each holding 50% of the shares. With the rise of domestic banking businesses, the growth of various premium businesses at SR Company has been showing a trend of rapid development. Due to the increase in the business of China’s insurance market system in recent years, the price war with bank charges and agency fees as the core and the improvement of the standard system required by banks have become increasingly fierce. SR Company also has some problems in the bancassurance business, especially in the marketing business. Such problems as lack of innovation and attraction in marketing methods and models, system and organization

models, marketing strategies, marketing means, and marketing products have caused significant obstacles and losses to the development of the company's bancassurance business. With the increasingly fierce competition in the bancassurance work market, the backwardness of the management concept and the lag of the marketing strategy model will undoubtedly expose the problems of SR Insurance Company more obviously. SR Company attaches great importance to the development of the bancassurance business and the occupation of market share, and it also attaches great importance to the competition with other counterparts. The mechanism, structural system, organizational system, personnel, business, and other aspects of bancassurance are improving, but there are still defects and problems on the whole, and various uncoordinated factors are gradually highlighted, affecting the rapid development of the company's bancassurance marketing.

Since the development of bancassurance in China, after nearly 20 years of rapid development, bancassurance has become a major business segment for insurance companies. At the same time, the bank agency channel has also become the sales channel of the insurance business, second only to personal marketing channels. Therefore, in order to expand their own premium scale and take a larger market share of the insurance business, various insurance companies and institutions have cooperated with banks in the insurance business. Therefore, most insurance companies are trying their best to win the favor of the banks, so as to launch fierce competition. What kind of marketing strategy and development strategy should insurance companies form in their bancassurance business to better manage this fierce competition while maintaining the healthy development of the insurance market and expanding their own interests? This is a very important issue. To this end, various insurance companies have increased innovative bancassurance business marketing methods, improved customer flow and insurance expenses, and hoped to gradually increase the market insurance share. Various marketing strategies emerge endlessly. However, given the current situation and development status of bancassurance, there are still many problems behind the rapid development of the business, which affect the stable and healthy development of the market and bancassurance and need to be solved in a timely manner.

While various insurance companies implement various bancassurance marketing strategies, many problems also arise. China's insurance marketing system still has shortcomings, exposing many defects, which has made it difficult to ensure the development of the entire insurance industry to a higher level and a wider field. The marketing channel system is not perfect, the marketing management lacks unity, the customers served, and products sold by various marketing agents are not clear enough, and there is a lack of mutual support and cooperation between various marketing agents or individuals, leading to conflicts between marketing groups from time to time. The support system of marketing strategy is not perfect enough, which leads to the lack of necessary means for the company to manage the marketing personnel at all levels.

SR Company is in a good position in the development and competition of the current bancassurance business in China, but there are also many problems. At the same time, with the strong development and pressure of other companies, the expansion and protection of its banking market are also unstable. In particular, in order to increase the market share of SR Company's bancassurance business, the company proposed various marketing methods, but the effect was not obvious enough. There were problems such as imperfect marketing strategies, insufficient marketing methods, and loopholes in marketing management and the structural system, which led to the stagnation of the company's banking business. Therefore, it is of great significance to analyze the marketing development status and problems of the bancassurance business of SR Company, analyze the factors and existing problems that affect the bancassurance marketing of our country, put forward strategic countermeasures to solve the marketing problems of SR Company, strengthen the bancassurance marketing effect of SR Company, and promote the expansion of the bancassurance business market of SR Company.

Literature Review

The foreign bancassurance business originated in France in the 1970s, developed in Europe in the 1980s, and gradually developed widely throughout the world. For the main business of this emerging financial industry, many international institutions and experts have fully studied it, especially the bancassurance marketing strategy to improve the business volume, which has been paid attention to and deeply studied.

Many scholars have studied the definition of bancassurance. Flur et al. (1997) defined bancassurance as the act of selling insurance products through banks and other sales channels. Subsequently, Skipper (2001) defined bancassurance as “*generally referring to the sale of insurance products by banks or the sale of banking products by insurance companies.*” Leach (1993) proposed that bancassurance is a service that includes traditional banks, savings banks, and housing construction associations to manufacture, market, and distribute insurance products. White (1998) defined bancassurance as an institution with a cross-shareholding of banking institutions, banks, and insurance companies, operating insurance products with asset management functions, and cross-marketing or selling any products or services that banking and insurance products can bring. According to Munich Re Group, bancassurance refers to providing insurance and banking products and services to a group of the same customers through a common sales channel (Benoist, 2002).

Ramasamy (2020) believes that the division of banking and insurance businesses stems from their different natures: banks mainly provide short-term and medium-term savings services, while insurance companies provide long-term savings services and provide insurance for various properties. In addition, both banking and insurance have strong independence and professionalism. The purpose of insurance is to manage and control risks. Therefore, the management of funds is only a by-product, and the management of risks is only an objective requirement of fund management. The bank is to manage and use the funds, ensure the security of funds, and increase the scope of application.

Levy (2020) believed that insurance companies managed their funds by investing in reserve funds, similar to banking businesses. Moreover, both insurance and banks are based on economies of scale and assume the function of risk transfer through reinsurance and refinancing. Therefore, these become the realistic basis for the integration and penetration of the two industries. Aikman et al. (2009) summarized the connection between banking and the insurance industry as follows: both industries operate reserve investment based on economies of scale, can create liquidity, can achieve large-scale capital integration and reinvestment, and can achieve risk management and profitability. Devi (2019) believes that bancassurance is a financial strategic task initiated by banks to serve banks themselves. Its purpose is to achieve the integration of banking and insurance within the same group by providing banking and insurance services to individual customers in the whole society.

Leale-Green and Bloomfield (1994) believed that bancassurance is a comprehensive financial service provided for individuals, units, and structures through the multi-industry combination of traditional banking institutions' work function business, the insurance business of insurance companies, and investment industry business (as cited by Chen et al., 2020). Leach (1993) believed that bancassurance was a financial service for banks and other financial institutions to develop and sell various life insurance products. Skipper (2001) believed that bancassurance was an arrangement between banks and insurance companies to sell insurance products through banks.

Overview of Domestic Research Status

The bancassurance business in China started in 1995. At that time, bancassurance only sold pension and term life insurance products at the bank counter, such as Ping An's “annual bonus pension insurance” (Ping An Group, 2021). From 1996 to 2000, it was the exploration and initial development stage of China's

bancassurance. Since 2001, it has been in a vigorous development stage. The cooperation between banks and insurance companies has been further expanded (Lee & Oh, 2020).

He and Zhang (2017) analyzed the life insurance marketing model of Guizhou Province under the trend of internet finance and put forward new marketing means to reduce the impact on the insurance industry, improve the way of life through insurance marketing, and deeply integrate insurance and the Internet. Chan (2009) pointed out that differentiated marketing can scientifically establish an emotional connection among insurance companies, policyholders, and banks, create a brand with affinity and trust, absorb more new policyholders, pay attention to the most valuable existing policyholders, and dynamically screen policyholders in the bancassurance business. Han and Li (2017) believed that the continuity of property insurance consumption, the accessibility of final customer information, and the accessibility of final customers make property insurance marketing more suitable for adopting the concept of relationship marketing.

In recent years, the competition in the domestic banking business has gradually expanded, and the number of insurance institutions and banks has gradually increased. The overlapping of businesses has caused many contradictions. For this reason, banks have put forward many targeted marketing methods for bancassurance businesses, and domestic scholars have studied many marketing strategies, mostly concentrated in universities and banking units.

Devi (2019) analyzed the influence of the bancassurance market environment, cooperation channels, and the future regulatory environment on business from the perspectives of market analysis, strategic choice, and business practice. At the same time, Devi (2019) made an in-depth analysis of the interbank competition environment and the needs of bancassurance customers and proposed the methods of bancassurance business marketing. Mwangi (2015) made a thorough and detailed analysis of the current development situation of a company's bancassurance business and the opportunities and threats faced by the company's marketing environment. Yingzhou (2012), through an in-depth analysis of the bancassurance business marketing environment of TB Property Insurance Company Shenzhen Branch, used SWOT-related methods to analyze the current marketing opportunities and threats, strengths and weaknesses of the company's bancassurance business, and proposed specific ideas and marketing countermeasures for TB's bancassurance business marketing strategy.

In addition, Buric et al. (2019), starting from the cooperative agreement type of bancassurance, not only analyzed its problems in the entrustment relationship and recommendation relationship but also analyzed the marketing and operation problems and proposed the sales strategy of bancassurance according to the existing shortcomings. Teunissen (2008) analyzed the main modes of international bancassurance cooperation and proposed that bancassurance marketing must be innovated.

SWOT Analysis of SR Company's Bancassurance Business

The SWOT analysis method, namely the situation analysis method, is also called the TOWS analysis method or Dow matrix and is often used for making strategic decisions for enterprises and analyzing the strengths of competitors. SWOT analysis includes strength analysis, weakness analysis, opportunity analysis, and threat analysis. It is an objective consideration of internal resources and the external environment when making strategic decisions. By analyzing the strengths and weaknesses of internal competition, as well as the opportunities and threats outside the enterprise, the enterprise can maximize its competitive advantages and external opportunities into enterprise power and try to avoid the disadvantages of the enterprise itself and the adverse factors brought about by the external environment. This will use the situation analysis method to analyze all aspects of the development of SR's bancassurance business so as to make more effective marketing strategies and improve the business level of the company's bancassurance business.

Analysis of opportunities and threats faced by SR company's bancassurance business

External opportunities refer to external factors beneficial to the development and operation of enterprises and the realization of their goals, such as national policies, economic conditions, and external business concepts and technologies. Under the current situation, the potential opportunities for the development of SR's bancassurance business include:

The domestic insurance market has been fully liberalized, and the insurance industry has entered a rational growth period. In the past decade, China's insurance market has gradually entered a stage of rational and stable development after the crazy expansion at the end of the last century. Especially since China's accession to the World Trade Organization (WTO) in the new century, China's insurance market has been fully liberalized, the insurance scale has shown sustained and stable growth, the market depth has been continuously deepened, and the number of market players has increased significantly.

With the development of network technology and the growth of e-commerce applications, it is imperative to use the network to market and develop the bancassurance business. The application of online banking has been comprehensively promoted, the public's awareness and application of online banking are also improving, and online banking customers are gradually increasing. The company's use of online banking to sell insurance products has become a major marketing measure. The company cannot only effectively contact a large number of potential customers by using online banking but also provide meticulous and thoughtful follow-up services to old customers who have bought insurance at any time, thereby reducing operating costs and improving operating efficiency. The cooperative sales of bancassurance products based on banks have greater advantages when using online banking. The insurance products are linked to online banking to facilitate customer demand. At the same time, due to the convenience of e-commerce, customers can open online services such as payment, inquiry, cancellation, and purchase of insurance products, which is convenient for operation and implementation.

From the perspective of asset scale, in 2018, the total assets of China's insurance industry were only 649.403 billion yuan. At the end of April 2004, the total assets of China's insurance industry exceeded one trillion yuan for the first time. By the end of 2021, the total assets of the insurance industry had reached six trillion yuan, 9.25 times that of 2018, and had become an important part of China's financial market. From the perspective of premium income, the national premium income in 2018 was only 305.3 billion yuan, and it will reach 1.43 trillion yuan in 2021, 4.8 times that of 2018, with an average annual growth of 18.7%. The insurance industry has become one of the fastest-growing industries in the national economy. In 2021, China's premium income will jump from the 15th place to the 6th place in the world, up to nine places from 2018. China's insurance market has jumped to a new starting point of development and has become an important emerging insurance market in the world.

From the perspective of the market system, in 2018, there were only 57 insurance companies in China. In 2021, the number of insurance companies will reach 158. Among them, there are 10 insurance groups and holding companies, 63 non-life insurance companies, 66 life insurance companies, eight professional reinsurance companies, and 11 insurance asset management companies. From the perspective of the national nature of insurance companies' capital, there are 98 Chinese-funded insurance companies and 60 foreign-funded insurance companies.

In 2018, there were 262 professional insurance intermediaries nationwide, reaching 2,554 in 2021, including 1,823 professional insurance agencies, 416 insurance brokers, and 315 insurance companies. It can be seen that China's insurance market has formed an insurance market pattern with diversified market players, resulting in deepening and continuous prosperity. The market size and total amount will continue to expand steadily, providing a good external environment for the development of SR's bancassurance business.

National regulatory policies were relaxed. After years of development, banking has become a global economy that attracts much attention. The development of the bancassurance business in China

started relatively slowly and experienced a period of great fluctuation. In recent years, with the promulgation of several opinions of the State Council on the Reform and Development of the Insurance Industry, the Memorandum of Understanding on Strengthening Deep-Level Cooperation and Cross-Industry Regulatory Cooperation between Banks and Insurers, and other relevant and important legal documents, policy support has been provided for the development of the bancassurance business.

At the same time, China's regulatory authorities are gradually opening up the restrictions on mixed operations. At the policy level, the regulatory authorities tend to relax the restrictions on mixed operations. The China Insurance Regulatory Commission has successively issued the Provisions on the Administration of Insurance Companies and the Measures for the Administration of Insurance Guarantee Funds, encouraging support for the mixed development of banking and insurance. The legal barriers to high-level expansion of the development model of banking and insurance will gradually disappear. The space for comprehensive operation will be greatly improved. It can be seen that the current in-depth development trend of China's bancassurance is largely due to the relaxation of national regulatory policies, and whether the subsequent bancassurance can continue to develop and grow steadily will also largely depend on whether the national policy environment is favorable. At present, the favorable factors in the national policies have prompted SR Company to develop in a more favorable direction in terms of cooperation mode, product sales mode, and product range.

Analysis of strengths and weaknesses of SR's bancassurance business

Internal advantage refers to the internal characteristics owned by the enterprise itself that can help the enterprise gain an advantageous position in market development and competition compared with other competitors of the same type, such as the quality of the company's internal management personnel, training mechanisms, customers, and sales network.

The bancassurance business of SR Company started in Dalian and has a traceable development history of more than ten years. In the development process, the bancassurance business of SR Company has gradually started with exploration and trial development and entered a stage of rapid development. The cooperative objects of the bank insurance business of SR Company are widely distributed, adhering to the concept of "preferred partner." SR Company mainly maintains a deep cooperative relationship with a commercial bank in Beijing. In addition, the company also maintains a certain bank insurance cooperative business with four major state-owned banks, post offices, and credit cooperatives, but its business proportion is small. In the development of SR's bancassurance business, the following internal advantages have given the company strong competitiveness:

1) Regional brand advantage of SR Company. SR Company is one of the first large-scale Sino foreign joint venture companies engaged in bancassurance business in northeast China since China's accession to the WTO and has also entered other domestic markets as a Sino foreign joint venture insurance company for the first time. It has good brand advantages in northeast China, Henan, and other places, and is the most advantageous brand in the Bohai Rim Economic Circle.

2) Operating cost advantage. As SR Company adheres to the principle of optimization when selecting bank partners, it does not participate in the crazy competition for bank outlet resources like other domestic insurance companies but implements focused cooperation investments. The company has launched a key cooperation with a bank in Beijing as one of its shareholders, and its outlet sales of life products are the first to be promoted by SR Company. With the bank's distribution of more than 200 outlets nationwide and the bank's good reputation and operating strength, most of the company's bank insurance product business plans can be completed, and the marketing cost is lower than that of other banks. In addition to Bank B in Beijing, SR also has a certain cooperation relationship with other banks. Due to the competition, most of the company's cooperation with other banks has been limited to one-year contracts,

and the company tries not to conflict with other insurance companies in terms of products, which reduces the cost of the company's investment in online banking marketing and improves cost efficiency.

3. SWOT analysis matrix. The development of the insurance business of SR Company can, to a certain extent, represent the development process of the domestic insurance industry in the new century. Under the current internal conditions and external environment, SR Company should reasonably choose the form of resource allocation and formulate a scientific and sustainable strategic deployment according to its own advantages. Through the above analysis, we have summarized the internal advantages and disadvantages, external opportunities, and threats of SR Company to provide a basis for the company to formulate strategic deployment.

The staff quality of the bancassurance business line at all levels of the branches of Company A is uneven, the marketing cooperation is not high, the functions are not implemented in place, and the lack of leadership, low quality, and other issues seriously affect the marketing effect of bancassurance, so it is necessary to establish a core leadership team for the company. The core leadership team construction is as follows:

1) Improve the leading departments of bancassurance. Strengthen the construction of the bancassurance organization of Company A, specify the leadership and leading institutions of the bancassurance business, and ensure that the leadership team has a clear division of labor, clear authority, clear work, and a clear division of work and cooperation. Set up bancassurance business development posts and support posts in all branches of Company A and select professional and high-quality leaders as leaders and guides in developing local bancassurance businesses.

2) Innovate the form of leadership organization and management. Strengthen the system construction and the company's internal assessment and training mechanisms; attach importance to the organizational ability, business ability, and professional skills of leaders; straighten out the business and departments of leaders and subordinates; and strengthen the banking and insurance marketing work and standardized management of leaders.

3) Strengthen core leadership elements. The core leadership team of bancassurance marketing shall be responsible for the guidance and arrangement of insurance planning, supervision, training, development, and other core posts.

From the combination analysis of internal advantages and external opportunities of SR Company, it can be seen that the domestic environment for bancassurance business is very favorable, which is conducive to SR Company taking advantage of its own advantages to implement the growth strategy. In the long run, only enterprises that choose the growth strategy can achieve the expansion of enterprise scale, while the implementation of the growth strategy requires increasing capital investment and making good use of external opportunities so as to improve the competitiveness of enterprises and expand market share. SR Company must adopt positive strategies if it wants to gain an industrial advantage in the banking business.

1) Give full play to SR's customer service advantages and good reputation; improve the training mechanism; further improve the service level; and form competitiveness. SR Company has built a perfect customer service system and organizational structure and has always attached importance to the customer satisfaction guarantee mechanism, making SR Company have a relatively large advantage in customer service and communication processing. At the same time, SR Company has high personnel requirements. Most of the banking business personnel have bachelor's degrees. In the personnel assessment mode, special attention is paid to service efficiency, surrender rate, and complaint rate. This measure has also kept the customer service level of SR Company's employees at a high level in the industry. In the nearly 10 years of the company's bancassurance business, customer complaints have rarely occurred. The surrender rate has also been controlled at the industry-leading level below 15%. It can be seen that SR is competitive in customer service.

2) Explore the development mode of bancassurance in line with national policies and legal requirements. The current policy and legal environment for bancassurance are very loose and favorable. SR Company should strengthen the research on the development model of bancassurance and choose a development model that conforms to the inherent law of financial development under a certain policy environment. This can help the company take the lead in the deployment and adjustment of future strategic decisions, seize the commanding heights of development, and avoid risks to the greatest extent.

3) Learn from the advanced experience of foreign bank insurance. Of course, it is not the foreign experience that can directly guide the development of the company's bancassurance business, but the actual situation of SR Company should be combined to develop strengths and circumvent weaknesses in product design, development mode, distribution channels, and technical support. In this regard, SR Company has the advantages of a foreign holding foundation and advanced operating experience in the insurance business under foreign financial groups. It should give full play to these two advantages to learn from foreign advanced banking and insurance operating experience to the maximum extent and participate in exploring a model suitable for the development of the company's banking and insurance business.

Conclusion

Product marketing occupies an important position in enterprise theory. Product is the core of marketing and the main thing to ensure share promotion and customer satisfaction. Therefore, when considering bancassurance marketing strategies, we should consider the elements of innovative bancassurance products and innovative marketing strategies for the products.

In the domestic bancassurance market, what is widely pursued and loved by customers is endowment dividend insurance products. When launching the bancassurance product business, major insurance companies will mainly consider endowment dividend products as the main marketing and expansion products. In this regard, the focus of bancassurance marketing is to strengthen the R&D, design, and marketing of dividend products of SR Company in combination with market demand and the current marketing situation of SR Company. The core advantage of SR Company lies in the operation of asset management companies. With the market fluctuation and the continuous rise of bank insurance reserve ratios, SR Company should strengthen the development of insurance products with banks and treat and market dividend products, universal insurance, and guarantee insurance separately. The current marketing strategy should focus on strengthening the marketing of dividend products.

The marketing strategy to strengthen the dividend products of SR Company is mainly to provide different types of insurance for customers at different levels and strive to obtain the largest market share of dividend bancassurance through effective marketing strategies. The market's potential customers are divided into children's, middle school age, college students, middle-aged, and elderly groups and treated separately. Different bancassurance dividend products are introduced for different age groups. At the same time, according to the risk resistance and economic affordability of customers, we should design and develop more dividend insurance products of the same kind and different natures for different groups. It aims at the needs of different people of the same age. For example, for children, we have launched Jixing Gifts Children's Endowment Insurance, Century Angel Children's Endowment Insurance, and Century Star Children's Endowment Insurance; For children's education, children's education annuity insurance is introduced; For middle school students and college students, we will launch high school education annuity insurance, college education annuity insurance and other products respectively, and give full consideration to parents' ideas and needs such as paying attention to children's education and future to launch different insurances of the same type; For the middle-aged group, due to their high level of knowledge, sufficient funds and open mind, we have launched various dividend products, such as lifelong insurance for family members and all risks insurance for rich and noble people; Various endowment insurance and pension annuity insurance are introduced for the elderly, such as loving life insurance, guarding life insurance and

other products. According to the above analysis and examples, it is the mainstream of current dividend products to launch bancassurance products for various groups of people to meet the needs of different groups, and it is also a strategy to expand the market and develop comprehensive marketing.

Therefore, in order to increase the market share of SR's bancassurance, strengthen the marketing strategy and development demand of bancassurance products, and strengthen the development and design of various dividend products, it is of great significance. In the process of SR Company's bancassurance marketing, the company should focus on the marketing of products with both financial management and security properties. For example, the company's universal regular payment products for rich and noble people, which have both the nature of high security function and financial management function, not only protect customers' insured objects from the perspective of insurance but also enable customers to develop the habit of regular savings to ensure customers' capital security and reasonable investment.

In the marketing process of bancassurance products, SR Company should pay attention to the combination marketing mode of security products and bank financial products and design professional investment plans for customers that meet their own needs, including security and financial management. On the basis of complete security functions and the purchase of satisfactory self-insurance, SR Company can also manage financial affairs with ease. In order to maximize the investment income of consumers and avoid investment risks as much as possible, banks should ensure that customers can transfer investment funds between insurance accounts and investment accounts in combination with the market environment. When the market is stable and the development trend is promising, customers can transfer more funds from a stable insurance account to an aggressive investment account. When the market is weak or the market outlook is uncertain, customers can transfer most of their own funds to robust insurance accounts to avoid risk and capital loss. The marketing model of this bancassurance product can ensure the customer's capital security to the maximum extent and avoid the customer's impulse insurance or surrender due to the impact of short-term earnings.

The incentive mechanism is the performance culture that best reflects the openness, fairness, and justice of insurance companies. According to Maslow's hierarchy of needs theory, the bancassurance channel of Company A should be based on the actual situation and give different incentives to insurance salesmen according to their different levels, positions, and responsibilities, so that they can get satisfaction and pride. At the same time, the incentive mechanism can also increase the income, position promotion, and spiritual satisfaction of marketing personnel, which can encourage them to work harder, improve their working ability more quickly, and create greater benefits.

To establish an effective incentive mechanism, we should combine the particularity of the work of bancassurance marketing personnel and encourage and improve the quality of the marketing team from the perspective of scientific career planning. The establishment of the incentive mechanism should change the traditional model and comprehensively consider the value relationships of dedication, performance, remuneration, and satisfaction. A performance appraisal system with the marketing value chain as the main connotation should be established, supported by a scientific and transparent incentive mechanism, to reasonably guide the enthusiasm of employees. The enterprise should establish a remuneration system for bancassurance businesses dominated by marketing value to positively stimulate the marketing team. The leadership team and management team actively formulate incentive policies for relevant marketing personnel, scientifically arrange marketing work plans, formulate marketing work objectives and incentive implementation methods, stimulate the morale of the sales team, stimulate their sense of responsibility and mission, greatly improve marketing skills and quality, and gradually evolve into a professional bank insurance marketing team.

For SR Company to implement this bancassurance marketing strategy with both financial management and security products, it is mainly aimed at middle-aged people or white-collar groups. The main measures are to conduct telephone, network, counter, and data bank business letter marketing methods for bank customer groups and credit card customers above the platinum level and to open customer financial

club services and organize authoritative financial and financial experts. It is specially designed for the middle class and white-collar people above the level of a long-term financial management plan to earn a good reputation for the sales of insurance and financial management business of SR Company so as to obtain more customer recognition and market share and further deepen the marketing of bank insurance business.

References

- Aikman, D., Alessandri, P., Eklund, B., Gai, P., Kapadia, S., Martin, E., Mora, N., Sterne, G., & Willison, M. (2009). *Funding liquidity risk in a quantitative model of systemic stability* (Working Paper No. 372). Bank of England. <https://www.bankofengland.co.uk/working-paper/2009/funding-liquidity-risk-in-a-quantitative-model-of-systemic-stability>
- Benoist, G. (2002). Bancassurance: The new challenges. *The Geneva Papers on Risk and Insurance – Issues and Practice*, 27(3), 295-303. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1468-0440.00172>
- Buric, M. N., Kascelan, V., & Vujosevic, S. (2015). Bancassurance concept from the perspective of Montenegrin Market. *Economic Review: Journal of Economics and Business*, 13(2), 62-73. <https://www.econstor.eu/bitstream/10419/193852/1/econ-review-v13-i2-p062-073.pdf>
- Chan, C. S. C. (2009). Creating a market in the presence of cultural resistance: The case of life insurance in China. *Theory and Society*, 38, 271-305. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11186-008-9081-1>
- Chen, P. S., Lee, J. J., & Pei-Fen, O. (2020). A study of Taiwanese banks' home loan life insurance attached to home loans. *Journal of Applied Finance and Banking*, 10(6), 225-239. <https://doi.org/10.47260/jafb/10611>
- Devi, P. P. (2019). Bancassurance: a marketing perspective. *International Journal of Civil Engineering and Technology (IJCIET)*, 10(3), 2093-2102. https://iaeme.com/MasterAdmin/Journal_uploads/IJCIET/VOLUME_10_ISSUE_3/IJCIET_10_03_209.pdf
- Floreddu, P. B. (2013). *Digital strategies for market dominance: Empirical evidence from the insurance industry* (Doctoral dissertation, Università degli Studi di Cagliari). https://iris.unica.it/retrieve/e2f56ed8-313b-3eaf-e053-3a05fe0a5d97/PHD_Thesis_Floreddu.pdf
- Flur, D. K., Huston, D., & Lowie, L. Y. (1997). Bancassurance. *The McKinsey Quarterly*, (3), 126. <https://www.proquest.com/openview/640d13e74843d7e14226517287aee05d/1?pq-origsite=gscholar&cbl=30375>
- Han, W., & Li, F. (2017). Influencing factors of analysts' property insurance demand based on grey relational analysis. In M. Zhang & H. Zhang (Eds.), *Proceedings of the fifth symposium of risk analysis and risk management in western China (WRARM 2017)* (pp. 369-374). Atlantis Press. <https://doi.org/10.2991/wrarm-17.2017.64>
- He, X., & Zhang, H. (2017). Research on life insurance marketing model of Guizhou province under the trend of internet finance. In T. Hee & J. Liu (Eds.), *Proceedings of the 2017 2nd international conference on education, management science and economics (ICEMSE 2017)* (pp. 356-359). Atlantis Press. <https://doi.org/10.2991/icemse-17.2017.88>
- Leach, A. (1993). *European bancassurance: Problems and prospects to 2000*. Financial Times Business Information.
- Leale-Green, H., & Bloomfield, J. (1994). Bancassurance: The shape of things to come. *Post Magazine*, 23, 16-19.
- Lee, J., & Oh, S. (2020). Analysis of success cases of InsurTech and digital insurance platform based on artificial intelligence technologies: Focused on Ping An Insurance Group Ltd. in China. *Journal of Intelligence and Information Systems*, 26(3), 71-90. <https://doi.org/10.13088/jiis.2020.26.3.071>
- Levy, H. B. (2020). Financial reporting and auditing implications of the COVID-19 pandemic. *The CPA Journal*, 90(5), 26-33.

- <https://www.proquest.com/openview/e78877503780f15b09adb4da7dbb4a54/1?pq-origsite=gscholar&cbl=41798>
- Mwangi, J. N. (2015). *Bancassurance: Strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats analysis and performance for commercial banks in Kenya* (Doctoral dissertation, University of Nairobi). http://erepository.uonbi.ac.ke/bitstream/handle/11295/94534/Njeri_Bancassurance%20Strengths%2c%20Weaknesses%2c%20Opportunities%20And%20Threats%20Analysis%20And%20Performance%20For%20Commercial%20Banks%20In%20Kenya.pdf?sequence=3&isAllowed=y
- Ping An Group. (2021, May 20). *China's first integrated financial services platform*. Ping An. <https://group.pingan.com/media/perspectives/China-s-First-Integrated-Financial-Services-Platform.html>
- Ramasamy, D. K. (2020). Impact analysis in banking, insurance and financial services industry due to COVID-19 pandemic. *Pramana Research Journal*, 10(8), 19-29. <https://www.pramanaresearch.org/gallery/prjp%20-%201632.pdf>
- Ricci, O. (2012). The development of bancassurance in Europe. In F. Fiordelisi & O. Ricci (Eds.), *Bancassurance in Europe: Past, present and future* (pp. 5-25). Palgrave Macmillan UK. https://doi.org/10.1057/9780230358287_2
- Richez-Battesti, N., & Leseul, G. (2016). Cooperative banks in France: Emergence, mutations and issues. In S. Karafolas (Ed.), *Credit cooperative institutions in European countries* (pp. 55-81). Springer International Publishing Switzerland. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-28784-3_4
- Skipper, H. D. (2001). *Financial services integration worldwide: promises and pitfalls*. OECD. <https://www.oecd.org/finance/insurance/1915462.pdf>
- Teunissen, M. (2008). Bancassurance: Tapping into the banking strength. *The Geneva Papers on Risk and Insurance-Issues and Practice*, 33, 408-417. <https://doi.org/10.1057/gpp.2008.22>
- White, M. D. (1998). What will it take for bank insurance to succeed in the United States. *North Carolina Banking Institute*, 2, 123-148. <https://scholarship.law.unc.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=1033&context=nbi>
- Yingzhou, L. (2012). *Research on the marketing strategy for bancassurance of TB Insurance Company Shenzhen Branch* (Master's thesis, Lanzhou University). <https://ir.lzu.edu.cn/handle/262010/210565>